

Why Choose Statistics as a Career?

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Abstract

In this poster, career pathways and the role of the statistician in various industries and types of jobs were explored. Statisticians in the pharmaceutical industry are key players in all areas of drug research and development. Examples were provided from review of literature and online reviews.

Key words

Statistician, pharmaceutical, career pathway.

1. Introduction

The word ‘Statistics’ had its origin from the Latin word ‘Status’. The word “statistics” comes from the modern Latin phrase *statisticum collegium*, which gave rise to the Italian word *statista* and the German *statistic*. Statistics is defined as the science of collecting, analyzing, presenting, and interpreting data. Statisticians analyze data and apply computational techniques to solve problems. Another definition “A statistician is a person who works with theoretical or applied statistics”. The profession exists in both the private and public sectors. It is common to combine statistical knowledge with expertise in other subjects, and statisticians may work as employees or as statistical consultants. If one aspires to work in a career where you can use mathematics to solve daily problems, a career as a statistician may be for you. A job as a statistician can be highly fulfilling with the ability to work in various industries. The key is to learn about the educational requirements for statisticians and the different responsibilities of a statistician which can help one determine whether the career is right for them.

1.1 Careers for Statisticians

Statisticians contribute to various industries such as insurance, pharmaceutical, banking, technology and sports. Actuaries that insurance companies hire routinely use statistics to make underwriting decisions. For example, given your background data collected actuaries can tell you how long you are expected to live. On the other hand, pharmaceutical statisticians design scientifically sound experiments or clinical trials to evaluate whether a particular pharmaceutical intervention is safe and effective against the disease of interest. The jobs that are projected to grow the fastest are shown in figure 1 below which shows the percent job growth.

Figure 1. The 10 jobs projected to grow fastest 2016-2026

1.2 Educational and Other Requirements for Statisticians

At a minimum, individuals interested in pursuing a career as a statistician will need a bachelor's degree in mathematics or an IT-related field with a concentration in statistics. A master's degree and a strong background in the industry will be useful. In general, MS or PhD in statistics or containing a significant statistical component is required based on the industry to which one is applying. Individuals with this background should be able to communicate statistical concepts and influence colleagues with other expertise (i.e., non-statisticians). Following the steps below will enable an individual to obtain a job as a statistician and achieve their career goals.

Step 1. Obtain a bachelor's degree

To qualify for a position as a statistician, many professionals have at least a bachelor's degree. Although a degree in statistics is one of the most relevant programs for a statistician, a degree in mathematics or another closely related field such as computer science also can help you qualify for this career path. Students in these degree programs complete courses like statistics, computer science, economics and applied mathematics. One can consider a minor or a second major to give you a competitive advantage in the field.

Step 2. Gain relevant experience

Gaining relevant experience can help differentiate you from other candidates when applying for statistician positions. If you recently graduated from college or are still studying, you can look for internship opportunities that provide college credit and apply your knowledge in a real-world environment. One also can look for competitions that allow you to test and demonstrate your abilities using real-world data. Competitions like these also can create opportunities to network with other professionals in the industry, which could lead to future job opportunities. They also can lead to invaluable mentorship opportunities.

Step 3. Consider an advanced degree

If you want to gain an advantage over other applicants and possibly pursue management roles in your field, consider pursuing an advanced degree, such as a master's or doctorate in applied mathematics or statistics. If you want to teach at a university, a doctoral degree often is necessary. If you plan to pursue a career in government or the private sector, a master's degree often can help you qualify for these positions. Consider researching current job openings in companies you're interested in to learn about the educational and experience requirements for those roles.

Step 4. Pursue professional certifications

Another way to gain a competitive advantage over other candidates for statistician job openings is to pursue professional certifications. These certification tests can prove to employers that you have the right skills to perform the responsibilities associated with a specific role. Some websites provide online certification programs you can complete, and many professional organizations offer courses you can complete to earn certifications. Consider researching the requirements and details of these courses to find one that fits your career goals.

Step 5. Learn programming

One can learn several programming languages that help individuals solve analytical problems more efficiently.

2. Skills for a Statistician

Statisticians use a range of hard and soft skills in their daily work to help them succeed. If you want to pursue this career path, consider developing these skills:

2.1 Communication

Statisticians often work closely with other professionals like chemists and engineers to solve problems. To work with those individuals successfully, they use excellent written and verbal communication skills. Statisticians also may explain complex statistical and mathematical methods to those who don't have an in-depth understanding of these subjects.

2.2 Problem-solving

Because the primary purpose of statisticians is to identify solutions to real-world problems, statisticians should have strong problem-solving skills. They often know which questions to ask, how to gather the right type of data appropriately and how to analyze that data. They then can interpret the results to make inferences and reach a viable solution.

2.3 Analytical

Statisticians use analytical skills to help them apply mathematical/statistical models and techniques when evaluating large amounts of data. Being able to analyze data and use it to arrive at an appropriate conclusion is important.

2.4 Mathematical Theory Knowledge

Statisticians may have a strong understanding of mathematical theories and methods. This can help them identify new and effective solutions to problems in science, engineering, business and other fields. Statistical approaches and theories employ mathematical concepts, so having expertise in many math functions can help you apply them.

3. How long does it take to become a statistician?

Depending on your education level, it typically takes four to six years to become a statistician. A bachelor's degree typically takes four years to complete, and a master's often takes about two years, depending on your program. If you choose to pursue a doctorate in this field, that can take you another four to five years to complete. You might be able to work in a statistician role while pursuing this degree.

4. Examples of Jobs

Below are few examples of job fields where statisticians can contribute:

4.1 In the field of sports

Preparation physically as well as strategically is a key to winning, and to this end professional teams gather as much data as possible. Some of the important data collected include, opposing team player statistics, recent wins and losses, which indi-

vidual players contributed to this win, weather conditions, game statistics. Role of a sport statistician in general is to help players, team managers, coaches and fans better analyze data to make decisions.

Qualifications

Sports statisticians may earn a bachelor's degree in mathematics, statistical analysis, data science, computer science or study a combination of these disciplines. An interest in and knowledge of sports is also important.

4.2 Environmental Statistician

The role of an environmental statistician is to observe and analyze data to find trends related to environmental science, that helps explain different phenomena and lead to better decision making on behalf of environmental scientists. Information gathered by environmental statisticians is used to influence climate change research and environmental policies.

Qualifications

Those who choose this line of work may pursue a variety of paths. To become a statistician, many individuals earn at least a bachelor's degree in statistics, computer engineering, mathematics, data science, or a related field. A background in environmental science is useful to this role, so those interested may want to take classes related to this field.

4.3 Biostatistician

Biostatisticians play a key role in the clinical trial process related to new medicines and vaccines. A biostatistician helps design, conduct, analyze and draw conclusions for clinical trials, to make more informed decisions. They calculate how many participants are needed for a trial, randomize patients into the intervention groups, determine which tools to apply to measure results, use appropriate methods to analyze the data and interpret the data to draw conclusions and communicate results to the relevant parties.

Qualifications

Individuals interested in working as a biostatistician may want to consider earning a medical degree, but a bachelor's in statistics, mathematics, computer science, data science or something related may suffice for medical statistician positions. Additional licenses or certifications may not be necessary for this job but could be viewed as a plus by potential employers.

5. Professional Organizations for Statisticians

Few professional organizations listed below which can guide the statisticians in job search as well as annual scientific meetings:

- American Statistical Association (ASA)
- Institute for Operations Research and the Management Sciences (INFORMS)
- International Statistical Institute (ISI)
- Association for Computing Machinery's Special Interest Group on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (SIGKDD)
- Institute of Mathematical Statistics
- American Mathematical Society

6. What Are the Pros and Cons of Being a Statistician?

Becoming a statistician can have its ups and downs. Statisticians can work in various industries. On the other hand, studying to become a statistician may be costly for some, given that jobs may require candidates to have a bachelor's and master's degree.

Pros

As a statistician, you will likely be asked to provide your expertise to teams working in a wide variety of fields and sub-fields, so you will get to become a mini-expert in each problem you're involved in. You engage the creative, analytical and social parts of your brain simultaneously on a daily basis.

Cons

Nobody knows what exactly statisticians do. The most popular response you'll hear is, "I hated the stats course I had to take in college." Additionally, working day in and out with complex data may be demanding.

Quick Facts: Statisticians	
Typical level of education that most workers need to enter this occupation	Master's degree
Job Outlook, 2021-31: The projected percent change in employment from 2021 to 2031. The average growth rate for all occupations is 5 percent.	33% (Much faster than average)
Employment Change, 2021-31: The projected numeric change in employment from 2021 to 2031.	11,200
The employment, or size, of this occupation in 2021, which is the base year of the 2021-31 employment projections.	36,100
Source: U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics	

7. Geographic Profile for Statisticians

Employment of statisticians, by state, May 2022

Source: U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics

Conclusion

Some of the advantages of being a statistician is great job prospects, monetary satisfaction, to be able to work in a variety of industries, to be able to interact and collaborate with colleagues from different backgrounds. Some statistician career path options are line management, technical expert role, project leader role. Individuals who are good working with numbers and analytical thinking should consider becoming a statistician.

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